

Navigating the AI Era in Higher Education

RHET AI Coalition Research Challenge #3
Emerging Tech, Ethics, and Higher Ed

May 2026

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About the RHET AI Coalition

The RHET AI Coalition brings together academics and industry to investigate the persuasive power of AI. Led by Arizona State University and the University of Tübingen's Center for Rhetorical Science Communication Research on Artificial Intelligence, founders include Stony Brook University and The Center for Humane Technology. The Coalition has since grown to include Auburn University and Missouri University of Science and Technology.

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Executive Summary

This RHET AI Coalition white paper urges higher education leaders to move from passive and presumptive acceptance of generative AI to active, informed agency. Rejecting both uncritical techno-solutionism and outright bans, it advocates for a deliberate approach that manages AI as a persuasive tool. This ethically grounded stance ensures that technology ultimately serves the deeper humanistic purposes of higher education: holistic student learning, the development of critical thinking and character formation.

Key Takeaways:

1. Manage AI as a Persuasive, Fallible Partner

Demystify AI by treating it not as an objective oracle, but as a highly persuasive co-author. This requires building a campus culture of human oversight, contextual awareness, and critical pushback so users actively manage the tool instead of passively trusting it.

2. Commit to Ethical Integration

Adopt AI only when it serves pedagogical values, not mere efficiency. Leaders must actively weigh the hidden costs—including global infrastructural inequalities, environmental impacts, and algorithmic biases.

3. Advance Rhetorical AI Literacy

Move beyond nominal "human-in-the-loop" models. Equip faculty and students with the critical agility to communicate with, evaluate, and orchestrate AI outputs, training them to challenge the systems' unfounded confidence.

4. Shift from Product to Process

Counter the outsourcing of thinking by redesigning class-assessments to value the intellectual struggle, transparent decision-making, and original thought over polished, AI-generated final artifacts.

5. Secure Strategic Relevance

To justify the value of a degree in an automated world, universities must position themselves as bastions of verified human rigor, producing graduates who pair technical skill with independent judgment.

Practice Portfolio

The included practice portfolio demonstrates that pedagogical AI integration is achievable, offering concrete examples to guide leadership toward conscious, deliberate choices about whether, why, and how to deploy generative AI on campus.

1 Purpose and Stance

Artificial intelligence (AI) has rapidly become a pervasive element in higher education. While the swift emergence of generative AI tools (like large language model-based chatbots) is often framed as an unstoppable evolution, their integration into academia remains fundamentally a matter of human choice and agency. This white paper is addressed to decision-makers in the higher education sector – administrators, department heads, and policymakers who determine which educational technologies are adopted – urging them to move from passive acceptance to active and informed decision-making. The paper rejects the false binary between uncritical adoption and Luddite rejection. Instead, it advocates a core stance of viewing AI as a sociotechnical configuration: the technology does not exist in isolation but in a complex world of research and innovation, market application, user experiences, and prevailing cultural myths (Kramer 2025). Stemming from this, the paper argues that AI integration must be guided by Rhetorical Pragmatism (Watson et al. 2024; Gottschling 2025) and Ethical Consideration (Burkhardt 2025a). The goal is a stance that recognizes AI's presence but insists its impacts be guided by educational values and an ethics inextricably linked to human thriving.

Public discourse on AI is frequently characterized by a simultaneous sense of anxiety and enthusiastic futurism (Voss 2021) – a tension intensifying as

AI systems transition from a “black box” technology to a conversational interface. Therefore, a central aim of this paper is to challenge and dismantle the idea that this technology is inevitable. As AI scholar Kate Crawford (2021, 8) argues, AI is not a neutral, autonomous force, but “both embodied and material, made from natural resources, fuel, human labor, infrastructures, logistics, histories, and classifications.” For Crawford, AI functions as a “registry of power” primarily steered by those who already hold influence. Higher education leaders, therefore, are not helpless passengers; they are pilots responsible for deciding if, why, and how AI should be used. AI's future in higher education depends on human agency and informed choice.

This decision-making process is fundamentally an exercise in grappling with the ethics of persuasion in technology adoption – examining who is convincing whom of what, and to what end, when it comes to AI in higher education. The paper's stance is that generative AI's presence cannot be accepted without being embraced critically. Rhetorically, this means treating AI not as a magic box that “automates” learning or improves efficiency, but as a tool that communicates – often persuasively and fallibly – within a human context. This rhetorical focus aligns with the necessary shift toward prioritizing purpose over product in educational design. When students can task an AI to offload the practical struggle

necessary to learn, the focus must shift away from what students produce and toward why an assignment exists and how students engage in the learning process (Watkins 2025). In this light, education is fundamentally about agency, and the advent of AI only heightens the need to help students find meaning and motivation in their intellectual struggles (Watkins 2025).

This white paper proceeds by addressing these challenges systematically. Section 2 offers explicit guidance for academic decision-makers by navigating the ethics of persuasion in technology adoption. Section 3 establishes the foundational ethical and humanistic goals, re-centering the discussion on education objectives and issues of global justice. The subsequent framework, detailed in Section 4, moves beyond “human-in-the-loop” oversight by proposing Holistic AI Literacy as the necessary theoretical foun-

ation. Section 5 presents a portfolio of concrete, process-focused interventions and practical examples. Finally, by foregrounding human agency and purpose in Section 6, the paper ultimately seeks to provide decision-makers with the vision needed to evaluate technological impulses from the Ed-Tech and Ed-Business sectors with critical discernment.

2 Guidance for Decision-Makers

This section addresses the stakeholders who set the strategic direction of higher education institutions. These figures – provosts, deans, CIOs, policy directors, and more – are the decisive agents empowered to shape how AI enters, or does not enter, their campus. While faculty and students influence daily practice, the choices about which tools to implement, which to forbid, and how to support their use lie with institutional leadership. A central thesis of this paper is that the future of AI in higher education will be shaped above all by the choices of institutional decision-makers. The paper urges leadership to reclaim agency in this technological moment, treating the integration of AI not as an inevitable evolution, but as a series of deliberate choices that must be justified by pedagogy and values. If higher education institutions simply slide into using every new AI tool out of fear of missing out, the educational mission is surrendered to commercial and technological hype. Instead, the institution must set the terms upon which it engages AI, aligning each adoption with a clear “why” and a thoughtful “how.”

First, recognize that the option to say “no” and reclaim agency remains available. This choice is not a simple rejection, but an assertion of pedagogical values that requires leadership to address the fundamental questions of how and why to integrate AI, rather than just if. Not every AI tool belongs in the classroom, and sometimes the most ethical choice

is restraint. The pressure to “keep up” can lead to what Evgeny Morozov popularized as technological solutionism – the tendency to seize on high-tech solutions for complex educational challenges. However, as Sætra and Selinger (2024) observe, this approach is characterized by “Promethean optimism about the revolutionary potential of science and engineering” and often functions as a type of social engineering – promising much but lacking imagined and presumed outcomes. This mindset views AI as the next step in educational evolution, a way to automate tedious work, personalize learning at scale, and gain a competitive edge. While efficiency and innovation are worthy goals, this stance often glosses over real pedagogical and ethical costs. Since how to offer effective education is what design theory calls a “wicked problem”: an intractable social challenge that technology alone cannot untangle. For example, adopting AI writing assistants wholesale could shortcut the development of students’ own writing abilities; automating grading with AI might erode the teacher-student feedback loop and introduce opaque biases. These risks are exacerbated by the tendency of both students and instructors to treat AI output as authoritative because it appears clear and confident, even when its underlying reasoning remains opaque and should be subject to human pedagogical scrutiny. At the same time, a purely technophobic reaction – banning all AI outright as “cheating” or inherently evil – may

ignore potential benefits and drive the problem underground (students will use the tools regardless). Between these extremes lies a spectrum of engagement. The following presents two perspectives on this spectrum, which are not mutually exclusive but place different emphasis on the challenge of AI integration.

The Technical-Critical View: The term “stochastic parrot,” introduced by Bender et al. (2021), describes large language models as probabilistic systems that mimic language without understanding. From this critical standpoint, generative AI lacks genuine comprehension, intentionality, or moral judgment – it produces plausible text based on patterns, but it does not know truth or evaluate right and wrong. This technical reality is often obscured by dominant narratives that frame these systems as an inevitable step toward AGI through a rhetoric of speed, disruption, and innovation. AI critics in this camp, drawing for example on Frankfurt’s (2005) concept of „bullshit,” argue that these systems function as entities that are fundamentally indifferent to truth. By framing AI as a „bullshitter” rather than a burgeoning mind, they shift the focus from the system’s perceived intelligence to its inherent lack of agency: its outputs remain weakly grounded in argument, with mere linguistic plausibility as its primary metric (Hicks 2024). In this view, narratives that frame these systems as an inevitable step toward AGI – or even as an existential threat – align with broader corporate interests by inflating the perceived power of the technology. Such „hype” rhetoric allows a small number of firms to use their control over compute and large-scale data extraction to consolidate not only market power, but also considerable cultural and political influence, increasing institutional dependence on systems that remain largely unaccountable. Stakeholders adopting this view remain highly cautious:

they see AI not as a potential superintelligence, but as a sophisticated form of autocomplete, useful for narrow tasks but fundamentally limited and potentially risky when relied upon for knowledge or fairness. Their stance therefore favors minimal entanglement: AI use should be permitted only in tightly controlled scenarios, reflecting a reluctance to outsource institutional expertise to systems that centralize power while offering little transparency or accountability.

Rhetorical Pragmatism: Along the lines of Gottschling (2025), a different perspective advocates for a rhetorical-pragmatic approach, treating AI as a functional co-author that, if used, must be integrated through explicit discourse practices and constant human oversight. This orientation is what is termed Rhetorical AI Literacy, recognizing that generative AI unequivocally requires an understanding rooted in classical rhetoric: the ability to assess context (*aptum*), exercise critical judgment (*iudicium*), and apply technical skill (*techné*). In this view, AI is neither a miracle nor a menace by default – its impact depends on how humans frame it, question it, and guide it. A rhetorical pragmatist acknowledges AI’s persuasive power, understanding that LLMs generate stylistic “persuasive surfaces” while only delivering probable arguments. Crucially, this perspective recognizes that the user’s prompt is not the sole source of framing; the system has already been shaped by developers whose design choices may reflect specific cultural norms and corporate priorities. The goal, then, is to foster a critical, reflective and reflexive dialogue in the user, moving away from passive acceptance. This requires recognizing the specific rhetorical agency of LLMs, particularly the “metacognitive illusion” – the tendency of AI systems to exude epistemic confidence with phrases like “I know” or “let me do that for you” – that emerges

in user interactions, thus increasing the likelihood of developing uncritical epistemic trust in the output (Erhardt 2025). Instead, a rhetorical pragmatist insists on wrapping any AI use in deliberate reflection and critical interrogation. For instance, an instructor might allow students to consult an AI for brainstorming but only alongside a reflection on the tool's biases and a comparison with scholarly sources. Administrators following this path will implement AI with clear policies and training: they'll choose tools that are aligned with institutional ethics (e.g., privacy-respecting, accessible), and they'll pair them with faculty development on how to prompt, interpret, and fact-check AI outputs. The key is seeing AI as a partner that requires active management – much like a junior collaborator who can generate ideas but needs supervision and correction.

In practical terms, rhetorical pragmatism means approaching AI use as an ongoing conversation. Rather than imposing AI or banning it outright, institutions foster campus-wide dialogue: What do we consider legitimate vs. illegitimate AI help? How do we credit or disclose AI contributions? How do we design assignments that leverage AI for exploration but still demand the student's own critical thinking? By treating these questions as rhetoric-infused, i.e., open to deliberation and context-dependent answers, decision-makers keep humans at the center of AI integration. This orientation is underpinned by the belief that while AI can generate content, only humans generate meaning and determine value. This approach attempts to forge a middle ground between the simple faith of uncritical solutionism and the wholesale refusal of the technocritical view.

Takeaway:

Decision-makers are not passive observers of an inevitable tech tide; they are responsible agents who must navigate the ethics of persuasion surrounding AI. The institution must critically evaluate the claims made by ed-tech companies, communicate the rationale (or lack thereof) for adopting a tool for its community, and ensure that technology serves, rather than subverts, the educational mission. In short, the future of AI in higher education will be determined less by the technology itself than by the leadership and vision (or lack thereof) of those steering its integration while keeping the ethics of persuasion at the fore.

3 An Educational & Ethical Primer

What is the ultimate *purpose* of education in an age of algorithmic systems? Before diving into literacy frameworks and practical classroom strategies, it's critical to remind ourselves of first principles – the humanistic and ethical foundations of why we educate in the first place. In the 19th century, Wilhelm von Humboldt, a German pioneer of educational reform, articulated the concept of *Bildung*, referring to the *formation* of the whole person through education, including moral and civic development. This ideal (dubbed *Humboldt'sches Bildungsideal* in German) sees higher education not merely as job training or information transfer, but as a crucible for self-cultivation, critical reasoning, and the pursuit of truth. This humanistic ideal is now challenged by systems that threaten to reduce learning to an exclusively transactional service, optimizing for speed and measurable output. By re-centering the discussion on *Bildung*, the paper deliberately adopts a conceptual framework that prioritizes formative goals (character, judgment) in stark contrast to the dominant market logic of the modern, often commodified, educational sector. As AI-driven tools threaten to reduce learning even more to transaction and output, higher education institutions must ask: Are they fostering *thinking individuals* and engaged citizens, or are they content to produce graduates who can efficiently generate answers with AI without demonstrating the underlying judgment and critical reasoning? The

(mis)use of AI in education is from this perspective not a surprise but rather an answer to a long-standing problem.

Consider the difference: A student who writes an essay by patching together AI outputs might get a decent grade on the “product,” but misses the formative struggle of grappling with ideas – precisely the struggle that shapes learning and affords genuine insight. If higher education yields graduates who have outsourced their reasoning at every critical juncture, the institution will have failed in its societal mission. Conversely, the key lies in intentionality: if institutions choose to use AI as a tool, this use must be conditional and subordinated within a broader framework of reflection and inquiry with potentiality to enhance students' ability to discern meaning and exercise judgment. The ideal of *Bildung* requires designing education such that every new technology is subordinated to the goal of developing *autonomous, responsible thinkers*. Thus, any use of AI in curricula should be measured against questions like:

- Does the use of this technology augment the intellectual, ethical, or creative judgment of students?
- Does it broaden their perspectives and deepen empathy?
- Or does it shortcut a necessary intellectual struggle thus stunting their growth?

Education as a Right and the Role of AI:

Education has long been recognized as a fundamental human right (per Article 26 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights). It serves not just individual advancement, but the public good – enabling informed, capable citizenry. Investing in education, particularly in ways that foster reasoning, critical thinking, and ethical discernment, is therefore an act of promoting ethics and supporting the ideals of good citizenship. In this spirit, the United Nations has designated “Quality Education” as the fourth of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals. It stipulates that “quality education and the promotion of lifelong learning” should be inclusive and equitable and should offer equal opportunities for all. With regard to the implementation of AI in higher education, this means that educators have to account for the diversity of students’ backgrounds and disparities in AI literacy, encompassing both access to and familiarity with AI tools – within individual societies and across different national contexts. The German Standing Conference of the Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs (*Kultusministerkonferenz*) (2009) emphasized that scientific and digital literacy are essential for empowerment in a democratic society. In today’s world, that extends to AI literacy: to participate fully in civic life and decision-making, people need a basic understanding of how AI systems shape information and choices they encounter. Therefore, educators must ensure that every student has equal opportunities to understand, access, and use these tools. This urgency becomes especially clear when AI begins to encroach on higher-order learning goals (e.g. following Bloom’s as well as Anderson and Krathwohl’s (1956/2001) taxonomy). If students can use generative AI to analyze texts, evaluate arguments, or draft essays, institutions must rethink how they distinguish genuine learning from the delegation of intellectual labor.

Technology has often played a dual role in this endeavor – and this tension is especially apparent in the case of AI. On the one hand, leveraging AI in education could help expand access and personalize learning, supporting the right to education on a broad scale, for instance through AI tutors that supplement teaching in under-resourced areas. On the other hand, if implemented carelessly, AI could exacerbate inequalities – offering a cheap, shallow learning experience to some (e.g., AI-driven large classes that lack human mentorship), while others get personal attention from professors who safeguard their burgeoning critical abilities. Institutional leadership must guard against AI becoming a mere cost-cutting tool that provides a second-class education to those less privileged. The promise of AI to widen access must not come at the price of hollowing out the quality and depth of the educational experience. If such is allowed, everyone loses.

Global and Epistemic Justice: Such an ethical lens must also widen beyond the campus. AI is entwined with issues of global justice – what technology scholar Kate Crawford calls the “registry of power.” When introducing AI tools, the question must be asked: *Whose power and knowledge do they amplify, and who might be harmed or left out?* This framing aligns with the ethicist Regina Ammicht Quinn’s (2014) principle that a technology is fair when the people enjoying its benefits are also those who bear the costs (not only monetary), provided these costs are distributed equally. Currently, the Global North benefits disproportionately from AI, while the Global South is disproportionately affected by related risks and harms (Burkhardt 2025a). This is compounded by the fact that there are actors not only from the Global South whose voices and stakes are severely underrepresented in debates about AI, limiting their ability to

shape technological futures (Burkhardt 2025b). These concerns, which range from the macro-level sociotechnical configuration to the micro-level impact

on the learning situation, reveal several critical justice issues for higher education.

Material and Global Justice: The External Costs of AI Adoption

- **Infrastructural Injustice:** AI depends on physical, digital, and labor infrastructures that are distributed highly unevenly across the globe. The benefits of these systems are concentrated in well-resourced regions and institutions, while many of the hidden labor and social costs – including forms of extractive data work and content moderation – are borne elsewhere (Burkhardt 2025a). For higher education, this means that adopting AI is never a neutral technical choice; it also means choosing to adopt AI leads to participating in infrastructures shaped by unequal access, asymmetrical labor conditions, and concentrated digital power.
- **Environmental Injustice:** AI systems carry substantial environmental costs, from energy-intensive model training and continuous server use to the material waste associated with digital infrastructures. These burdens are not shared equally but fall disproportionately on vulnerable communities already exposed to climate-related harm. For institutions, this means that large-scale AI adoption should also be treated as an environmental decision, requiring reflection on the necessity, scale, and the often-hidden carbon costs – a calculus frequently ignored by well-resourced institutions eager to signal innovation.
- **Economic Injustice and Commodification:** The most powerful AI models and infrastructures are controlled by a small number of large technology companies, creating clear risks of institutional dependency. In higher education, this can reinforce an educational monoculture shaped by corporate priorities and deepen the commodification of teaching and learning in ways that directly conflict with humanistic educational aims. Decision-makers should therefore weigh not only convenience and cost, but also questions of vendor dependence, governance, labor impact, and the value of open or locally controlled alternatives.

Pedagogical and Epistemic Justice: The Internal Costs to Learning

- **Social Injustice and Bias:** AI systems are notorious for encoding biases present in their training data. For decision-making AI (like automated admissions algorithms or scholarship selection tools), this raises red flags of discrimination. And of course generative AI used in class can produce stereotyped or one-dimensional content – reflecting social, historical, and structural inequalities, as well as representations and non-representations embedded within the data. This extends beyond merely “missing voices” in discourse that educators regularly address. It also involves the system’s responsiveness: it caters to the needs of the prompt and the prompter, meaning that if the user is unaware of the specific context they are prompting about, the model will not necessarily correct oversights and may generate a response that is inappropriate for the situation. Educators must be prepared to highlight these biases and help students detect whose voices are missing in AI outputs.
- **Epistemic Injustice:** AI tends to reinforce existing knowledge hierarchies. For instance, English-language content is vastly overrepresented in training data, which means AI systems privilege Anglophone perspectives. Niche or indigenous knowledge, or non-digitized wisdom (like oral traditions), are often invisible to AI. There is a danger of AI flattening rhetorical diversity and extraordinarily hastening the loss of indigenous knowledges, as it converges on mainstream styles and ideas. In an educational context, this could subtly discourage students from exploring or valuing knowledge outside the algorithm’s “comfort zone.” However, this issue is complex, as some scholars argue that a certain degree of uniformity in academic writing could be viewed positively in research for the purpose of better comparability and scholarly rigor. Nonetheless, in the context of education, educators should actively counter this by encouraging students to bring in sources and examples beyond what AI easily provides, and by critically examining the absences in AI outputs. Whose stories are not being told by the chatbot? Whose worldview is being taken as default?

Yet the justice question is not exhausted by diagnosis alone. Under carefully structured conditions, generative AI can also function as an assistive resource for students whose participation is shaped by disability, neurodiversity, or other structural barriers. This potential, however, remains conditional: AI should extend human support, not replace it. For example, an AI-based transcription tool can help a deaf student take notes from a lecture, or a text-generation tool might help a student with dyslexia brainstorm ideas without the barrier of spelling. These companion technologies can be wel-

comed, as long as they are implemented with the student’s agency in mind (the student controls the tool, and it’s augmenting rather than replacing human support). At the same time, caution is warranted against seeing AI as a cheap substitute for proper accommodation. The presence of a writing assistant does not eliminate the need for writing tutors; a text-to-speech AI doesn’t replace providing materials in accessible formats. Decision-makers should ensure AI is used to enhance accessibility in tandem with, not in lieu of, robust support services.

We hold that the solution to a problem should not cause bigger problems than originally existed (Ammicht Quinn 2014). If we introduce AI to solve an educational issue (say, grading workload), we must ensure that solution doesn't, for instance, create a justice issue or erode educational quality in a way worse than the original problem. In ethical terms, this is akin to the medical principle "first, do no harm." As the German Ethics Council (2023) aptly noted regarding AI use in educational settings, digitalisation should never be an end in itself and

the use of AI tools should be grounded by fundamental educational values that prioritize the "formation of personality." That is, we shouldn't deploy AI just because it's trendy or because others are doing so; there must be a clear, justifiable benefit that outweighs the costs and risks.

Takeaway:

A flourishing life – for our students and society – depends on an education that prioritizes human judgment, creativity, and ethical discernment over algorithmic expediency. This pursuit is urgent in a sector where education is increasingly treated as a commodity, but generative AI's tendency to expose underlying biases and false shortcuts offers a critical moment to re-assert a foundational humanistic purpose. Any integration of AI must be evaluated in light of core educational values. The central negotiation is agency: The institution must not ask if the technology itself supports the principle of holistic personal formation (which would be an impossible demand for any tool), but how its deployment can be structured to support the objective of developing autonomous, responsible thinkers. In the end, the flashy new tool might just be a step backward in disguise. The difference lies in who controls the narrative: Do we let the AI dictate what education becomes (cheaper, faster, but shallower)? Or do we insist that our humanistic goals dictate how AI is permitted to operate in our classrooms? Our answer is clear: human agency and ethics must lead, technology must follow.

4 Beyond the “Human-in-the-Loop”

A common mantra for safe AI deployment is to keep a “human in the loop.” In theory, this means that no AI system operates fully autonomously – a human oversees outputs and makes final decisions. While well-intentioned, this model cracks under stress if the human in question lacks the knowledge or attentiveness to catch AI’s mistakes. The current reality is that AI systems like advanced chatbots produce answers or analyses so stylistically persuasive that educators and students may be unable to tell when they are wrong. If an instructor themselves cannot discern an AI-generated hallucination from a fact, the human-in-the-loop safeguard fails. The *crisis of the loop* is thus: we risk leaning on AI for efficiency, saying “don’t worry, a human checks it,” while that human is increasingly inclined to trust the AI or lacks the critical literacy to challenge it.

Furthermore, this perspective fails to account for the multiple “humans in the loop” who produce and receive AI-generated texts. Because generative AI often produces texts meant for other human readers, it does not simply assist communication; it inserts itself into the communicative relationship, mediating

and potentially distorting the exchange. When AI introduces persuasive argumentative fragments whose origins necessarily evade critical scrutiny – co-intentionalities (Gottschling 2026) – the loop multiplies, and the problem shifts toward one of mediated discourse and control.

To move beyond a simplistic “just add a human” approach, we need to upskill the human. This is where a rhetorically informed conception of AI literacy becomes essential, re-centering the discussion on agency and on how learners and institutions retain intellectual control in the face of technological expediency. We must address how to prevent the user from becoming a mere component in the machine’s loop – a pawn in the game. This foundation recognizes both the option to decline the use of AI outright and the capacity for its reflective integration. Countering the uncritical acceptance of machine outputs – which can manifest as “click thinking” (Falasca 2025) – requires a comprehensive framework.

Holistic AI Literacy (Falasca 2025, Falasca 2026) is the framework relied upon in this paper. This model moves beyond tool proficiency by integrating three core dimensions: media literacy (evaluating source credibility), critical AI literacy (understanding biases and ethical issues), and rhetorical AI literacy (communicating *with, about, and through* AI). The framework encourages educators and students to treat AI outputs as texts to be interrogated: *Who* wrote this, for *what* purpose, and *what* might be missing or misleading? Similar calls for structured AI-aware pedagogies appear in university-focused work by Kasneci et al. (2023), who argue that assessment design must explicitly address when AI use is appropriate and when it undermines learning goals.

Generative AI systems function as persuasive technologies whose rhetorical shortcuts can lead to over-trust and “templated thinking,” flattening diversity (Veldhuis et al. 2025; van Noort et al. 2024). Thus, the cultivation of effective AI literacy must include explicit instruction in rhetorical discernment, positioning this competence as a civic and epistemic practice. These include fact-checking activities that require students to verify or correct AI outputs, comparisons of shallow vs. deep reasoning, or bias-identification tasks. These and more interventions for the classroom are described in the following chapter.

The most pressing challenge across education is cognitive offloading – the outsourcing of the practical struggle necessary for learning – which risks eroding critical thinking and intellectual virtues (Naeem 2024; Gerlich 2025). Emerging research also indicates a growing disconnect between students’ frequent use of generative AI tools and their ability to critically evaluate AI-generated outputs (Falasca 2026). Decision heuristics are vital to guide not just decision-makers, but students as they seek to determine when AI is pedagogically valuable and when a task *must* remain human-led. To counteract authoritative, shallow AI outputs (Falasca 2025), structured frameworks must train students to interrogate accuracy and ethical implications, fostering deliberate, reflective engagement. The Holistic AI Literacy framework aligns with Critical Digital Pedagogy by prioritizing reflection, agency, and social responsibility, and by supporting forms of AI-responsive pedagogy that are equitable, ethical, and justice-oriented (Kumbhakar et al. 2024; Barrot 2024; Daher 2025). In this sense, Holistic AI Literacy provides the broader educational framework for addressing generative AI responsibly. Within that shared framework, Rhetorical AI Literacy brings a more focused emphasis to questions of language, persuasion, and communicative agency. Because generative AI operates through language and persuasive form, the ability to communicate with, about, and through AI becomes especially important for higher education.

Competent use of generative AI tools requires a shift in mindset: generative AI should be understood not as a simple tool, but as an active contributor within a process of hybrid authorship (Gottschling & Kramer 2025). Yet it lacks access to the broader situation and context that inform both what we know and what we communicate about.

While the user operates within a rich, contextual environment, the chatbot works only on a reduced representation of that “messy” context.

The competence required to bridge this gap is the ability to orchestrate generative AI.

Rhetorical AI Literacy equips educators and learners to address this challenge by cultivating three core classical competencies in the context of AI:

- **Process Knowledge (*techné*):** The technical skill necessary to engage the tool. This is achieved by adopting a mindset of co-authorship to acquire process knowledge, primarily through a strategy of AI orchestration. This involves an iterative cycle of a) prompting, b) dialogic negotiation, and c) appropriation, emphasizing sustained dialogue, iteration, uptake, and correction in the feedback loop.
- **Situational Appropriateness (*aptum*):** The contextual responsiveness required for effective communication. This involves compensating for machine “context-blindness” through human verification of social and situational appropriateness. It addresses the fact that the LLM output is often disconnected from the specific situational requirements of communication. Users must evaluate the artifact to ensure it aligns with the communicative context – a task made inherently challenging by the fact that many students are themselves still novices learning to navigate these exact communicative needs.
- **Critical Judgment (*judicium*):** This competency necessitates sharpening critical judgment to evaluate AI outputs and assume full editorial responsibility. It integrates critical media literacy, which is essential to transform skepticism into the productive application of generative AI while ensuring epistemic and professional integrity. The practice of verification is critical here, especially in light of persuasive metacognitive illusions (Erhardt 2025) – the tendency of AI systems to exude epistemic confidence that discourages user critique and reflection.

The ultimate goal of Rhetorical AI Literacy is for educators and students to cultivate a specific form of reinforced human agency. We conceptualize this as resourcefulness and the strategic agility to navigate algorithmic systems without losing intellectual rigor (Gottschling 2025; Coeckelbergh 2018). In this sense, resourcefulness becomes a cultural practice in which technical skill (techné) and strategic action serve not just to solve problems, but to reclaim human intent from the prescriptive nature of algorithmic defaults.

A competent user of generative AI possesses this strategic agility and is

therefore able to use the system for exploration while critically evaluating and building on its outputs through independent research and judgment. This ensures that rhetorical production as techné does not devolve into technological hubris, but remains tied to human judgment and responsibility. Such competence, however, does not emerge automatically; it is a capacity developed deliberately over time and through sustained cognitive effort.

Takeaway:

Agency in the AI era rests on robust literacy and critical agility, not on simplistic human oversight. A merely nominal “human-in-the-loop” is insufficient if that human cannot exercise discernment; instead, we need humans in control of the loop – through comprehensive AI literacy education. Our ability to benefit from AI without being duped or deskilled will hinge on developing Rhetorical AI Literacy as resourcefulness and strategic agility within higher education. This means equipping students and educators with the wisdom to know when to use AI and when not to, and with the rhetorical discernment and critical savvy to question and manage the persuasiveness of generative AI.

5 Practical Interventions

Re-Focusing on Process

Having established *why* we must approach AI in education carefully in the preceding sections, this chapter turns to the *how* – an exploration of the diverse rhetorical and pedagogical techniques available for critical engagement with the *ethics of persuasion* embedded in generative AI systems. The aim of the following portfolio is not to provide a step-by-step implementation guide for instructors, but to demonstrate that pragmatic-critical approaches to generative AI are both possible and pedagogically productive. In this sense, the portfolio serves as a proof of concept for decision-makers, showing why institutions must not simply enable AI use, but must establish the frameworks and conditions that enable such critical engagement.

A central theme of our recommendations is the necessity of re-focusing on the learning process instead of just the final product. In an era where students can generate a polished essay or problem set solution at the click of a button, traditional metrics of assessment (the final paper, the correct answer) lose their reliability as indicators of learning performance. We must design assignments and evaluations that value the process over the answer, the underlying unders-

tanding, and the students' intentional decision-making. The most critical question guiding this shift is: What does it mean to deceive oneself by using generative AI?

The challenge posed by AI is that it encroaches on the highest levels of Bloom's Taxonomy: students can prompt an LLM to *analyze* a text, *evaluate* an argument, or even *create* new content. This risks a fundamental *self-deception* – an exchange of the intellectual struggle necessary for learning against algorithmic expediency. The exercises in the portfolio are designed to use this challenge as an object of reflection, encouraging learners to critically examine the *ethics of persuasion* that govern AI's outputs, define the limits of appropriate use, and ultimately refocus on the value of human intellectual effort. The pedagogical outcomes of these practices must include the informed decision by both faculty and students to reject the use of generative AI when its persuasive force or outsourcing potential is deemed detrimental to learning.

This shift in educational focus requires the cultivation of process knowledge and critical dispositions that cannot be outsourced, moving toward.

- **Protecting Higher-Order Learning Goals:** Assignments must be redesigned to actively counter cognitive offloading. The goal is to move beyond merely requesting the creation of an artifact (a final paper or a presentation) and instead demand explicit evidence of the students' thought process, intentionality, and original contribution.
- **Emphasizing Rhetorical and Dialogic Methods:** Inquiry-driven and active learning methods become essential because they engage students in unpredictable, real-time thinking that is difficult to outsource (labs, debates, case studies) to a static AI prompt. These are fundamentally rhetorical methods focused on listening, reacting, arguing, and navigating complex situations.

This reorientation calls for more than procedural skill alone. Incorporating generative AI into the classroom should cultivate habits of skeptical scrutiny and active human creativity, because students need both in order to avoid being misled by its persuasive rhetoric and to remain intellectually engaged in the learning process (Naeem 2025; Gerlich 2025). Building on the principles of Rhetorical AI Literacy, this means encouraging students to question an AI's first answer, verify and correct its claims, and use its outputs as starting points for further refinement rather than as substitutes for their own judgment. If AI provides a generic solution, the student's task is to challenge it, build on it, or add the situated perspective the system itself lacks.

In short, generative AI requires a proactive, institution-wide shift in how learning is assessed. Moving beyond reactive policing, including overreliance on flawed AI-detection software, means reorienting

academic culture away from the final product alone and toward the student's process, agency, and decision-making. When the focus shifts to why and how students produce knowledge, AI becomes less a threat to be managed than a complex partner whose outputs demand human judgment and critical engagement. This approach is essential not only for preserving academic integrity, but also for teaching students responsibility in an AI-augmented world. Crucially, it reasserts that faculty are indispensable to the learning process, rather than mere inefficiencies to be resolved.

Praxis Portfolio: Intervention Blueprints

The following portfolio of interventions serves as a proof-of-concept. These models demonstrate that faculty can successfully adapt their pedagogy to tackle the rhetoricity of generative AI – its capacity to produce fluent, structurally sound, and highly persuasive output that frequently masks

a lack of factual grounding or deep reasoning. For institutional leaders, these frameworks represent scalable strategies to foster critical AI literacy, preserve academic integrity, and re-center human cognition – in all its facets – in the learning process.

1. The Research-Based Launch: Confronting AI Overreliance (*Jennifer M. Santos*)

Before introducing specific assignments, classes can benefit from grounding AI policies in empirical research rather than punitive rules.

The Framework:

Instructors present students with data regarding AI overreliance and ask them to evaluate and rank the findings based on their potential impact. The exercise uses specific research conclusions demonstrating negative correlations between frequent AI use and critical thinking, problem-solving, exam performance, and overall academic achievement (Abbas et al., 2024; Bastani et al., 2024; Gerlich, 2025; Lee et al., 2025).

Strategic Value:

This approach shifts the conversation from academic dishonesty to cognitive impact, providing an empirical foundation for why structural guardrails are necessary to protect student learning capacity and agency.

2. Policy Engagement and Ethical Reflection (*Laura Dumin*)

Institutions frequently struggle to get students to read, let alone internalize, campus-wide AI and academic integrity policies. This framework transforms policy compliance into an active, credit-bearing academic inquiry.

The Framework:

Students are tasked with reading the university's official AI policy and defining "academic misconduct" in their own words. They then complete a researched reflection detailing their past AI use, predicting their future use for academic tasks, and analyzing how AI tools will impact their specific future workplace. This assignment is bracketed by pre- and post-semester reflections to track shifts in their ethical understanding.

Strategic Value:

This approach shifts the conversation from academic dishonesty to cognitive impact, providing an empirical foundation for why structural guardrails are necessary to protect student learning capacity and agency.

3. Transparency Appendices & Reflection Journals

(Laura Dumin, Marina Falasca, Jennifer M. Santos)

Rather than attempting to catch AI use after the fact, this policy shifts the focus of assessment to the research, drafting, and interrogation process itself.

The Framework:

Students submit “proof of process” alongside their final work. A Research Appendix mandates PDFs of all sources with cited passages highlighted. An AI Prompt-Reflection Journal requires full transcripts of interactions with generative AI (treating the tool as a “study buddy”). Students must document their initial prompts, critical counter-prompts (e.g., “Check your sources,” “Why omit this perspective?”), and a final evaluation of the platform’s utility.

Strategic Value:

Documented transparency naturally establishes academic integrity. By making the invisible process visible through prompt transcripts and critical counter-prompts, this framework provides an audit trail for critical judgment and shifts the grading focus to the student’s interrogation of the tool.

4. Factcheck the Bot: Cultivating Epistemic Vigilance

(Laura Dumin, Marina Falasca, Jennifer M. Santos)

This intervention flips the traditional assessment model: instead of the instructor testing the student, the student tests the machine.

The Framework:

Instructors provide students with an AI-generated essay or dataset containing subtle biases, cultural blind spots, or hallucinations. Students engage in structured bias-identification tasks, cross-referencing the AI’s claims against verified course materials to distinguish between the machine’s “shallow” reasoning and human “deep” reasoning.

Strategic Value:

This intervention turns the inherent flaws of generative AI—such as hallucinations and bias—into an active pedagogical asset. Engaging in this process reinforces rigorous research skills and instills a campus-wide culture of verification against the metacognitive illusion.

5. Breaking Bad: Stress-Testing AI Limits to Prevent Misconduct (Markus Gottschling)

This sandbox exercise allows students to safely explore the absolute boundaries of generative AI, effectively demystifying the “magic” of an automated term paper.

The Framework:

Students role-play a scenario where they must rely entirely on generative AI to produce a data-driven term paper from scratch. They prompt the AI to conduct a literature review, synthesize a dataset, run a statistical analysis, and write the interpretation. They then audit the final product to find where the illusion falls apart.

Strategic Value:

Serving as a high-impact risk education intervention, this sandbox allows students to proactively discover the limitations of end-to-end AI reliance, such as the generation of false citations. Experiencing these failures firsthand provides persuasive evidence that unchecked dependence on generative AI is a form of self-deception, strongly reinforcing the need for human agency.

6. Full-Cycle AI Production: The Multimodal Commentary Poster (Jennifer M. Santos)

This exercise embraces maximum AI integration, shifting the student's role from sole author to "creative director" and auditor of fully AI-generated multimedia.

The Framework:

Students are tasked with creating a persuasive commentary poster (using platforms like Canva) from start to finish using AI. They identify a minor daily irritation related to their major and use AI to brainstorm all content: labels, causes, solutions, and counter-responses. They must also generate specific AI images to match. While the drafting process is entirely AI-assisted, students are still required to submit a rigorous Research Appendix to verify any factual claims made in the poster.

Strategic Value:

Embracing maximum use of generative AI for brainstorming, drafting, and design still demands strict human audit and editorial responsibility. This exercise proves that the "AI-as-co-pilot" model is highly viable, provided institutional frameworks mandate clear documentation and critical process oversight.

Takeaway:

The challenge of generative AI requires a fundamental shift in pedagogical culture from valuing the final product to valuing the student's process, agency, and intentionality. To counter cognitive offloading and support on-going development of critical thinking, assignments must protect higher-order learning goals and demand explicit evidence of critical judgment and strategic agility. This focus on critical dispositions and the student's informed decision to use, or reject the use of generative AI is essential to preserve academic integrity and intellectual rigor.

6 Strategic Outlook

Beyond the Academy

Higher education does not exist in a vacuum. The decisions we make about AI in the classroom echo into the broader world that our graduates will enter. In this final section, we zoom out to consider the larger strategic landscape: the job market and societal context, the value proposition of universities in an AI-driven future, and the crossroads ahead for the role academia might play.

It is almost a truism now to say that *“there is no going back to a world before AI.”* Today’s jobs are already being redefined by AI and tomorrow’s jobs will be even more so. As AI adoption — and even the expectation of it — reshapes routine entry-level work in fields ranging from journalism to law to accounting, higher education is increasingly forced to confront an existential question: How will people work in the age of AI? Employers will increasingly expect graduates to know how to use AI tools relevant to their profession, and to do so effectively as well as responsibly — whether in marketing, scientific research, or other fields. The challenge is not merely one of technical skill, but above all of judgment.

That higher education must answer this question can be seen either as the result of the increasing commodification of the college degree or of its weakened responsiveness to the challenges faced by middle- and lower-income families — which of these interpretations one finds more persuasive is itself something of a cultural Rorschach test. Regardless, colleges and universities have worked strenuously in recent years to do just that: articulate the value of their degrees. Most metrics around this value center on measures and signals of employability; as average rates of tuition outstripped inflation, prospective students and their families have demanded figures on return-on-investment. These typically include statistics like the lifetime value of a degree, the percentage of students employed or in graduate school within six months of graduation, and the like. But if universities fail to adapt to an automated work landscape, or adapt in ways that compromise genuine cognitive and ethical development, the perceived premium and value of a college degree may erode.

Success-oriented storytelling was necessary even before AI began to decimate entry-level jobs. Now it is imperative. And so higher education institutions are forced, then, to answer intertwined, existential questions: First, why should people go to college; and second, what kinds of jobs will a college education prepare students for? Beginning with the first question requires a further assumption: If higher education is more than just about employability after graduation, what, exactly is that “more”?

In our recommendations, we have aligned our answer with a humanistic view of education as *formation*: creating informed, engaged citizens who are capable of critical thinking, as well as open to and appreciative of people with different life experiences. Answering that question now requires doing so against the backdrop of continually declining trust in institutions as well as the evolution of AI. The proliferation of AI-generated content – from deepfakes to mass-produced posts – has created an authenticity and information crisis. The answer also involves communicating the value of such institutions within a functioning society. From the standpoint of audiences outside academia, higher education often has limited ability to make its case in purely philosophical terms, which means that the second core question – what kinds of jobs will universities and other institutions prepare students for? – often has to be answered first and in demonstrable ways. Whether one agrees with that logic or not, it shapes the external conditions under which higher education must make its case. Only on that basis can institutions more productively invi-

te students into the first, more philosophical question of why people should go to college at all.

To answer this second question, universities must articulate their enduring value by serving as bastions of verified knowledge, where research and output carry a badge of “human rigor” that automated content lacks. But if answering the first question boils down to helping students make sense of a world increasingly fueled by AI, then higher education must also help them make sense of the digital world that surrounds them. Much like universities once had to integrate computer skills to ensure that graduates were not left behind, we must now treat AI literacy as the new computer literacy though, as this paper has shown, with a holistic and especially rhetorical focus. This entails helping students understand not only the difference between media created by AI and by humans, but more importantly the implications of those differences: the motivations of content creators, the consequences of repeated disconnects from reality, and the broader conditions under which such messages circulate. They must be able to decide for themselves the value of those messages and the credibility of their sources. That, in turn, can enable students to reflect more critically on how they value information and where they place their trust. A more deliberate and habitual consideration even of casual social media content can foster a wider practice of critical analysis directed at the world around them – including the institutions that uphold a functioning democracy. Higher education offers a uniquely multi-disciplinary backdrop

against which those values and habits of discernment can be developed, tested, and refined.

Relatedly, if some in-class experiences become AI-enabled experiences at the same time that term papers become functionally obsolete, then perhaps old ways of working return to the fore in college classrooms. Because universities offer something irreplaceably human and communal, if students engage regularly in rhetorical debate and doctoral-like discussions even at the undergraduate level that require their deep subject knowledge and rapid-processing abilities, they may just graduate ready to use AI as a tool, not a replacement for thinking. By freeing up classroom time from mere content delivery, institutions can double down on original research, hands-on projects, and artisanal scholarship.

But to get students to college, it is imperative to answer that second question: What kinds of jobs will higher education prepare them to get? That requires telling stories that make that answer clear. This storytelling must speak not only to employment rates after graduation, but also to the kinds of jobs students go on to hold, including clear examples of how they use AI, how they deliberately do not use it, and why those differences matter. In practical terms, institutions should tell their story in a new, formative way: “We don’t just give you knowledge; we shape how you think. We certify not just that you know specific facts, but that you have learned how to learn, unlearn, and discern.”

Ultimately, society will increasingly grapple with whom to trust, and higher education’s task must be to cultivate educated human experts who use automated systems wisely. While many institutions still dance around this issue, leaders at both the high end of the market — the MITs of the world — and the local and regional end — the community colleges offering associate’s degrees in AI — are already moving forward. They understand the opportunity, the value, and the significance of doing so for their continued relevance. Yet, it must be noted that for the elite institutions driving this charge, this innovative posturing frequently glosses over the severe environmental and infrastructural injustices outlined earlier. Meanwhile, the more hesitant institutions appear to be waiting for some unmistakable signal that now is the time. If declining enrollments and intense competition for a shrinking student pool are not that signal, it is hard to know what would be. It may be, however, that many such institutions — and many individual faculty members — remain silent simply because they do not yet have those stories to tell. After all, to tell such stories, institutions must first create the conditions that make them possible. This requires a strategic commitment to faculty well-being and a shift away from cultures of punitive surveillance of both students and faculty, which can inadvertently stifle the very pedagogical risk-taking needed to navigate this transition. Only through the kinds of methods outlined here, and perhaps others besides, can they truly do so.

To build these stories systematically, institutions must intentionally navigate two strategic paths: the Ethical-Critical Path, in which they act as moral bastions that scrutinize AI's power dynamics, and the Rhetorical-Pragmatic Path, which emphasizes skillful co-activity and innovation. Ideally, institutions will combine these approaches through

robust internal governance. Their ability to enable such stories may well determine not only whether higher education continues to exist in its present form, but also what role it will play in the future.

Takeaway:

To maintain relevance in the AI era, higher education must proactively answer two intertwined, existential questions: Why should people go to college? and What kinds of jobs will a college education prepare students for? The institution's strategy must prioritize demonstrably answering the market-driven job question to win the external audience. Only then can it productively frame the philosophical question by establishing AI Literacy as a foundational component of modern citizenship and demonstrating how it equips graduates with the critical discernment and strategic agility necessary to thrive in an AI-augmented world. This perspective aligns with emerging research in graduate education suggesting that AI competence should not be understood merely as technical proficiency with AI tools, but rather as the outcome of sustained AI literacy development that integrates critical, ethical, and communicative capacities (Falasca 2026, Limongi 2026).

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Imprint

RHET AI Coalition White Paper #01

Navigating the AI Era in Higher Education

Published May 2026

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20026436

Published by

RHET AI Coalition // *rhetai.com*

In collaboration with:

Center for Rhetorical Science Communication Research on Artificial Intelligence (RHET AI)
at University of Tübingen

Responsible for content according to German Press Law (V.i.S.d.P.):

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Cover photo: Silvester Keller for RHET AI Center

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The editors would like to thank Carolin Saia, Klara Hartmann, and Roger Thompson for their feedback, with special thanks to Carolin and Klara for their additional suggestions, and to Carolin for her valuable work formatting this white paper.